

Review Article

Authenticity and Adaptation of Instructional Materials in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Class

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Abstract

The importance of materials in language teaching and learning has been extensively acknowledged, its culturally-specific content in which all norms, values and standards as well as beliefs of learners are taught in relation to the content. It is culturally or locally-relevant because learners will be able to relate them to their own everyday-life situations and experiences so that they are meaningful to them. Also, adaptation process has offered some great advantages, but the researchers and educators failed to identify its limitations and drawbacks and left behind the consequences it may bring about, only focusing on theoretical frameworks, principles, technique and overlooking the idea of how such adapted materials will practically influence the effectiveness of language learning in a wide variety of learning contexts. Teaching materials are a key instrument in most language courses. This paper presents an overview of the use of authentic materials in the English as a second/foreign language classroom and their significance for language learners. It also examines the concept of material adaptation, criteria as well as its limitations in the English as a second language classroom.

Key words: *authentic material and adaptation, instructional materials, foreign language*

Received: 10 March 2018

Accepted: 08 May 2018

Introduction

English Language Teaching (ELT) materials are of significant importance for foreign language education. They determine the quality and quantity on input, the affective and cognitive involvement of learner in the language learning process, what is to be taught, language teaching, methodology, syllabus organization, teacher training and learner training (Grossman and Thompson, 2008). Language is enough comprehensible samples of a language (Krashen, 2012). That is why choosing the appropriate ELT materials is of great importance in an EFL country like Nigeria, where ELT materials are the main means of obtaining English language input. In today's global world, learners have more chance to be exposed to English in their daily lives. Computers, internet, media, and films are some means through which learners receive authentic input (Mishan, 2005). However, they are not so common yet and not everyone has access to them. Nor are they systematically organized to facilitate language learning. Since they are authentic and have no language teaching purpose, they are generally incomprehensible for learners. Thus the quality and quantity of English input learners receive are generally limited with what ELT materials provide to students. It can be concluded that EFL materials shape how much and what kind of input EFL learners are exposed to, and consequently determine the rate and level of language acquisition to a great extent (Krashen, 2012). It is also pointed out that for a successful language education; affective factors are at least as important as the input factors (Krashen, 2008).

It is stated that the level of interest determines the level of motivation and high level of student interest ensures high motivation (Yuen, 2011). ELT materials, which offer instruction that is sensitive to learners' linguistic levels, provide variety and present information in a comprehensible and enjoyable manner, increase the involvement of learners in the teaching/learning process and predict the success level in L2 (Hernandez, 2006). For example a group of computer engineering majors at an English medium university in an EFL country attended an English preparation class in order to follow the academic programme. The needs of these students are focused on a specific field. Throughout their education they will study books on computer programming and do computer related tasks. So, the materials ought to foster the students' academic language skills to support their education in their field. These students not only need language skills but also initial background knowledge and terminology in their field in order to experience a smooth transition to their subsequent education by getting academically, cognitively, and linguistically prepared and ready for the next year. If they study English by using general ELT materials, it is obvious that this kind of education cannot prepare them for

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their subsequent education (Mishan, 2005). Thus, the match between the materials and learners' needs and also fosters both cognitive and affective involvement of learners and predicts the success level in L2 (Richards, 2012). Hence, ELT materials and classroom activities should meet the linguistic, cognitive, and academic levels and interests of learners and be designed in such a way that learners can easily relate themselves to them and have optimal exposure to L2 (Yuen, 2011).

Furthermore, the research has shown that it is important to give voice to students in the management of their learning (Tomlinson, 2003). Learners are a part of the teaching-learning process and inevitably have preferences in their language classes as all human beings do. They are aware of their wants and when they are given a chance to verbalize them, they can contribute a lot to the language program. This is especially true when the students actively participate in the materials selection process through different means such as piloting certain parts of ELT materials, questionnaires and interviews. They begin to believe that their ideas are valuable and they have power over the language materials selection process. Consequently, they psychologically take ownership of the learning process. If in fact the class atmosphere is created by the teacher, the learners and the materials, the value of choosing the most relevant materials by the active participation of learners in the materials selection process can create the most optimized learning experience (Mishan, 2005). Students feel that the materials are not imposed on them by an authority, but that they are the result of their choice. Hence, a kind of positive attitude towards the material can be fostered and a close match between materials and learner characteristics can be achieved which make classroom tasks more meaningful, purposeful, and enjoyable. It can be concluded that if a language program is to be successful, the program must carefully take into account the means in which learners participate in the materials selection process.

Concept of Authentic Material

The term authenticity and authentic are often used to describe language samples—both oral and written—that reflect the naturalness of form, and appropriateness of cultural and situational context (Rogers and Medley, 1988). The term authentic materials may mean different things for different people; for some, materials generated by native speakers and for native speakers are considered authentic (Rogers and Medley, 1988). Throughout the history of English language teaching (ELT), authenticity is taken as being synonymous with genuineness, realness, truthfulness, validity, reliability, undisputed credibility, and legitimacy of materials or practices (Tatsuki, 2006). It has also been a major feature in syllabus design, task-based approaches, materials development and the main focus of the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in

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the past (Bax, 2003). In the words of Grellet (1981, pp. 8-9), “Authenticity means that nothing of the original text is changed and layout are retained. ...Exercises must be meaningful and correspond as often as possible to what one is expected to do with the text”. Authentic materials appear in various course books in two forms: un-doctored and doctored-pseudo-authentic materials. Adaptation on the other hand is defined as a process in which published teaching and non-teaching materials are changed, modified and suited to particular groups of learners in particular in EFL learning situations.

Characteristics of Good/Authentic Textbooks

All good and authentic material has got the characteristics of having the language input and skill development; positive impression in learner’s mind; useful information to deal with language; an easy familiarity; a thought provoking insight; a remedy and improvement in the deficiencies of the learning outcome; and a sense of security and confidence to the language teachers. Widdowson (1978) defines authentic text as the reader’s response. It is more important than whether it is simplified or not. According to him, coherence contributes to the authenticity of a text, and it depends on the reader’s response. For whether simplified or not, if the reader is able to react to the text, then only can the text be considered authentic. The learner is a necessary factor in all consideration of understanding of meaning or reading, emphasizing the fact that meaning is personal to the reader and ‘authenticity lies in the act of interpretation’ (Widdowson, 1979, p. 165).

While Hutchinson and Waters (1987, p. 107) maintain that ELT materials provide a stimulus to learning; help embody a view of the nature of language and learning; reflect the nature of the learning task; can have a very useful function in broadening the basis of teacher training; and provide models of correct and appropriate language use. Tomlinson (2003) outlines the characteristics of good materials as follows:

- a) materials should achieve impact
- b) materials should help learners to feel at ease;
- c) materials should help learners to develop confidence
- d) learners should perceive learning materials as relevant and useful
- e) materials should require and facilitate learner self-investment;
- f) learners must be ready to acquire the being taught
- g) the learners’ attention should be drawn to linguistic features of the input
- h) Materials should provide learners with opportunities to use the target language to achieve communicative purposes, through meaningful, realistic interaction

- i) Materials should consider the positive effects of instruction to be delayed, thus incurring recycling; materials should be attentive that learners differ in learning styles
- j) Materials should deliberate that learners differ in affective attitudes
- k) Materials should permit a silent period at the begging of instruction
- l) Materials should maximize learning potential by encouraging intellectual, aesthetic and emotional involvement which stimulates both right and left brain activities
- m) Materials should not rely too much on controlled practice; materials should provide opportunities for outcome feedback.

McGrath (2013) contends that the importance of materials-as-content act as a stimulus for communicative interaction, and materials-as-language serves the purpose of information about the target language and carefully selected examples of use. According to him, following are the advantages of textbooks: reduce the time needed for lesson preparation; provide a visible, coherent programme of work; provide support; a convenient resource for learners; make standardized instruction possible; visually appealing, cultural artifacts; and contain a wealth of extra materials. According to Tomlinson (as cited in Ahmed, 2016), 'materials' are inclusive of anything which can be used to facilitate the teaching and learning of a language. They can be linguistic, visual, auditory or kinesthetic, and they can be presented in print, through live performance or display, or on cassette, CD-ROM, DVD or the internet. They can be instructional, experiential, elucidative or exploratory while informing learners about the language, providing experience of the language in use, stimulating language use or helping learners to make discovery about the language for themselves.

While supporting the idea that teachers should prepare their own materials, Howard and Major (2004) present a set of guidelines for designing effective materials for teaching and learning English: English language teaching materials should be contextualized; Materials should stimulate interaction and be generative in terms of language; English language teaching materials should encourage learners to develop learning skills and strategies; English language teaching materials should allow for a focus on form as well as function; English language teaching materials should offer opportunities for integrated language use; English language teaching materials should be authentic; English language teaching materials should link to each other to develop a progression of skills, understandings and language items; English language teaching materials should be attractive; English language teaching materials should have appropriate instructions; English language teaching materials should be flexible.

According to Harmer (as cited in Ahmed, 2016) course books have the following advantages: sensibly prepared to offer a coherent syllabus, adequate language control, motivating language use with supplementary materials; often nicely presented; a source of some dependable materials under pressure; have got detailed teacher's guide providing not only lesson plans but also suggestions and alternatives, extra activities and resources; adoption of a new course book offers a great stimulus for methodological development. Cunningsworth (1995) analyses the role of materials in language teaching as: a resource for presentation materials; a source of activities for learner practice and communicative interaction; a reference source for learner on grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation etc.; a source of stimulation and ideas for classroom activities; a syllabus; and a support for less experienced teachers lacking self-confidence. Hall (2011) believes that well-designed textbooks have a number of recognizable benefits for teachers and learners since they provide language input and exposure for learners; offer interesting and motivational material, organized in an appealing and logical manner; arrange for a written record of what has been studied, allowing revision and continued study beyond the classroom; and also reduce time teachers require for preparation. He also observes that accessibility to computer and web-based technologies are increasingly blurring the boundaries between the textbooks and new technologies. Kitao and Kitao (1997) believe that materials are valuable in that they act as course organizers; lesson organizers; teacher's tool for reaching the learners; sources of information as well as sources of ideas.

Moreover, Ansary and Babaii (2002) argue in favour of using texts as a textbook is a framework which regulates and times courses/programs; as no textbook means no purpose in the eyes of learners, also without a textbook learners think their learning is not taken seriously. Garton and Graves (2014) contend that course book: gives structure to lessons and to a course; saves time; gives a sense of security; promotes autonomy as learners can use and refer to it outside the classroom; is reliable as it is written by experts and published by well-known publishers; gives a sense of professionalism in a way it is presented; offers different perspective as it focuses on diverse cultures and places.

Various other writers have pointed to particular functions fulfilled by textbooks. They play a major role in supporting and complementing the teacher, as well as supporting the learner. As a result, the most commonly found elements in ESL/EFL classrooms around the world are teachers, learners and textbooks. Since textbook or materials are such a key component of language classrooms, their suitability and effectiveness deserve critical attention (McGrath, 2013).

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Some Culturally Familiar Ideas for Language Development

Tasks can contribute to creating a congenial environment in the classroom. A task is "an activity or action which is carried out as the result of processing or understanding language (i.e. as a response) ... The use of a variety of different kind of tasks in language teaching is said to make language teaching more communicative ... since it provides a purpose for a classroom activity which goes beyond the practice of language for its own sake" (Richards and Schmidt, 2010, p. 584). Long (1985, p. 89) defines a task as a piece of work undertaken freely or for some reward. Breen (1987, p. 23) identifies a task as any structured language learning endeavor which would naturally have its own objectives, content, working procedures and outcomes. When Nunan (1997, p. 10) describes a task as basically "a piece of classroom work which involves learners in activities like comprehending, manipulating or interacting in the target language". While selecting the materials for tasks in the classroom, following are the issues that should be taken into consideration: relevance; authenticity; focus on processes; potentiality for active roles; feasibility in the classroom; level of the learners. Long (as cited in Farrell and Jacobs, 2010, p. 61-62) emphasizes that tasks should be authentic in that the tasks students do in the class should mirror the kinds of tasks they are or might be doing in the outside world.

The emergence and widespread use of technology has made it possible for the language teachers to get access to various sources quite easily and quickly. Familiar and authentic situations and functions can enable learners to interact, communicate and participate in the classroom with ease and comfort. The following familiar and common ideas can be used quite effectively in a language class covering all the four skills, such as, listening, reading, speaking and writing.

Listening Skill

Morley (2001) suggests that an appropriate aural comprehension programme that targets learner listening at all levels of instruction is an essential for second/foreign language learning. She further opines that the following four perspectives could be incorporated in any ESL/EFL listening courses: (a) Listening and repeating (b) Listening and answering comprehension questions (c) Task listening (d) Interactive listening.

Hedge (2003) argues that contrived listening texts have features which in no way are accurate to real spoken language. If students hear only unnatural language in the classroom, their first experience of hearing authentic spoken English in real life can be demoralizing. Here classroom can provide a conducive environment of learning in

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which authentic texts can gradually be introduced and utilized to build learners confidence.

As Hedge (2003, p. 68) finds the following common topics for intermediate level current course books for listening skills, they could be quite helpful for the classroom as authentic materials: radio plays, news items, children's stories, travel news, weather forecasts, airport and station announcements, radio talks, debates, extracts from recorded guided tours, relaxation tapes, exercise instructions, interviews etc.

For developing listening skill there are huge resources on different TV channels which can definitely help learners develop their listening informally. Channels like BBC, National Geographic Channel, Animal Planet, Discovery, Adventure1, Star Plus, HBO, CNN, AXN, CN, ESPN offer news, interview, talk show, travel show, movies and sports commentary which informally help learners develop general comprehension in listening. Most importantly, by using these resources learners can be familiar with variety of English's used in different countries.

Reading and Writing Skills

Grabe and Stoller (2001) recommend that the choice of primary texts and textbooks, supporting resources, classroom library materials have a major impact on students' motivation to read and their engagement with reading. Hedge's (2003, p. 68) list of the following common topics for intermediate level current course books for reading skills could be also quite helpful for the classroom as authentic materials: letters, recipes, menus, newspapers, articles, train timetables, horoscopes, advertisements, publicity brochures, postcards, street maps, route maps, yearbook entries, weather forecasts, curricula vitae, theatre programmes, poems, instructions for use of equipment etc.

With regard to teaching writing, Brown (2001) poses an important question of how much of the classroom writing is "real" writing. Following are some activities that could be undertaken for the developments of reading and writing skills:

- (a) Local English newspaper clippings, magazines, advertisements, brochure, flyers, common informative literature of different well reputed organizations;
- (b) Post-colonial writings, popular fiction, comics and visual novels for reading;
- (c) Students' writings for identifying and correcting mistakes;
- (d) Job advertisements for job applications and CV writing
- (e) Any official documents related to job offer, essay and report writing.

Speaking Skill

Lazaraton (2001) maintains that while teaching speaking skills, teachers need to be specifically proficient in organizing class activities that are authentic, motivating, and varied. The use of authentic, engaging materials should be the basis for in-class activities. Following are some of the speaking activities for an adult language class:

- How traditional marriages are organized - function-language focus-vocabulary connectives.
- How to cook favourite and other popular local/international dishes.
- How to play 'various games or cricket or football.
- How to wear a tie, kimono, Indian shari, turban.
- Describe some social occasions like: different religious festivals, popular and cultural marriage and other ceremonies around the world.
- Describe some problems like, load shedding, drug abuse, terrorism, corruption, student politics, cheating and plagiarism, traffic jam, local/international political leaders.
- Describe your favourite personalities like, a person who you consider very successful, who you feel greatly indebted to, your dream lady/man.
- Describe some successful organization like Facebook, Apple, Microsoft, Grameen Bank, BRAC, World Bank.
- Describe your favourite band group, shopping center, restaurant, game.
- Give your own suggestions about how the practice of giving and taking bribe can be stopped.
- Give your own view about the statement like 'arranged marriage is much safer and happier than love marriage'.
- Some real life situations: describe your daily routine of life, narrate how you spent the day when you got your Higher School Certificate result or imagine yourself 10 years later from now.

A material design model consists of four basic principles (Hutchinson and Waters, 1987): input (starter), content (text), language (function) and task (activities). If we apply all these to our culturally appropriate situations, it appears to yield a positive feedback. At the same time teachers can provide useful vocabulary in order to smoothly run the communication.

The above mentioned materials are some items which can be developed as authentic materials for English language classes alongside existing materials being used from other sources. It is imperative to begin with an overview of existing curriculum and syllabus and then how other materials can supplement the process of language

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learning. Dubin and Olshtain (1986, p. 29) sets five basic components to examine a language programme (i) the existing curriculum and syllabus (ii) the materials in use (iii) the teacher (iv) learners and (v) the resources of the programme. Furthermore, while developing a material for language teaching one has to go through several steps like: selecting grading, sequencing implementing, and evaluating materials. Some basic questions for evaluating materials: (a) by whom and where are the materials developed? (b) Are the materials compatible with the syllabus? (c) Which language skills do the materials cover? (d) How authentic are the text types included in the materials? (e) How do the learners and teachers feel about the materials?

Harmer (1998) also pointed out some criteria for evaluating a material that might be essential for learners and trainee teachers. The points considered in Harmer's evaluation form are practical consideration, layout and design, activities, skill, language type, subject and content, guidance and conclusion. Each of these criteria has got some questions with sample answers. These criteria can be extended with some more points, for example, level of learners, role of teacher and learners, any advantage/disadvantage etc.

Material Adaptation

The need to adapt or modify the use of given textbooks and other language teaching materials to fit the requirements of particular learning situations, and even particular students, is widely recognized. This volume presents a systematic approach to adaptation useful for methods courses as well as for the experienced teacher or curriculum planner. As the first principle of effective adaptation, maintenance of congruence between varieties of factors is stressed; these factors include the teaching materials, the methodology and objectives of the course, student characteristics, the character of the language being taught, and the personality and style of the teacher. Adaptation according to Krashen (1982) is also a process, which involves certain criteria to become effective in learning. Murray and Christison (2011) state that "...textbooks do not always drive the teaching-learning process, but rather provide a scaffold on which teachers and learners can build. Because textbooks are mostly written for a wide range of learners, teachers find they need to adapt a textbook that they or their institutions have chosen. This may include making changes to activities and texts in the textbook or supplementing the textbook with additional materials, either from other sources or written by the teacher".

In this context Richards (2002), states that commercial textbooks can hardly be used without some adaptation to make them more suitable for the particular context of their

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usage. Language teachers need to build this essential skill of adapting commercial textbooks in the following procedures: modifying content, adding or deleting content, reorganizing content, addressing omissions, modifying tasks, extending tasks etc. (as cited in Ahmed, 2016). A course book is a learning tool shared by teachers and learners that can be used in systematic and flexible ways. In order to use a course book systematically and flexibly, it is important to understand how it is put together and how it can be adapted to meet the needs of the particular learners. A course book is not an inflexible document; it is a learning tool that is used by learners and teachers. The decisions about what to “select, adapt, reject and supplement” depend on who the learners are (age, interests, purposes for studying and language level), what the institution emphasizes, the available resources, duration or time frame, and what is important (Graves, 2003).

In this connection, Harmer (2007) is of the opinion that many teachers want to use course books as a kind of facilitator for their lessons, rather than as a manual to be mindlessly followed, i.e. they use the course books as a main basis for lessons while they have the option to decide when and how to use its essential parts (as cited in Ahmed, 2016).

Criteria for Materials Adaptation

The following form the cornerstone for adapting authentic materials.

- **Adaptation should facilitate instruction:** Teachers sometimes find their authentic materials difficult and unsuitable to teach due mostly to lack of harmony in subjects, incongruity of subjects and given teaching methodology, etc. Materials should, thus, be instructionally easy to implement. The pedagogic presentation of materials, as one of the key factors that can underscore the effectiveness of materials in foreign language settings can enable teachers to adapt the suitable teaching methodologies, models and techniques to them in a variety of learning situations. Teachers can employ them to facilitate the learning process by consciously choosing what is theoretically and practically true and apt to teach. It is in this criterion that teachers reword instructions as to materials in order to make them more accessible or acquirable, manageable, understandable, analyzable, digestible and communicable to learners.
- **Adaptation should encourage learning:** Sometimes, learners complain that they cannot learn what they have studied during the term. Authentic materials seem to be richly structured, replete with lots of passive and unfamiliar words and complicated discourse. Thus, they should be developed according to the level of students. They should be designed unambiguously so as to boost learners’

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- comprehensibility as well as their self-confidence. They should enhance the learners' learning awareness. They should also inform learners of how well they have performed and how they have progressed.
- **Adaptation should focus on learners:** Because authentic materials are not designed according to learners' needs most often, learners give no special care towards what the materials convey, or it is difficult for learners to communicate with the content. Since the notion underlying the currently-favored teaching models and methodologies have stressed the learners' role in the learning process, students' needs, interests and views should be included in designing the materials. Pedagogically, there are two types of materials development. The first is the Negotiated syllabus which is internally generated or the product of the negotiation between teacher and students, and the second is externally imposed syllabus, which is the syllabus imposed by an external body such as the teacher, an institution or any other administrative authority. In authentic materials, everything is infused into the learners. They are imposed by authorities in charge, which carry their thoughts, demands and decisions, degrading the active role of the learners. According to the current studies, the development of a language course curriculum should be adapted to the learning preferences and expectations. So the focus is supposed to be on the materials designed as result of a negotiation or a mutual understanding between both parties, i.e., the learners and the teacher. In this case, the materials and learners are at the center of the learning process and make them the main input providers.
 - a) **Adaptation should ensure relevance:** Materials should be relevant because they should be worth teaching. They should be aligned and suited with the planned course objectives or with what is expected of. What is being taught, as Krashen claimed, should be perceived by learners as relevant and useful. Moreover, they should have the same effect with different groups of target learners.
 - b) **Adaptation should prompt flexibility:** Authentic materials are not as flexible as expected as the learner styles, needs and learning environments are sure to change. Materials should be flexible so that teachers will be able to easily adapt what they teach to agree with a particular setting and a particular group of learners. In other words, teachers should provide learners with 'the possibility of choosing different activities, tasks, projects and approaches, and therefore of adapting the materials to their own preferred learning needs'. (Alamri, 2008, p.15).
 - c) **Adaptation in terms of motivation:** The issue of whether the materials are motivating is not easy to decide on by itself. The materials can motivate

learners when all of the aforementioned criteria are taken into account. The lack of any one of the above will result in learners' demotivation, not necessarily in the lack of motivation but in a state in which learners gradually feel that they are losing their motivation because any one of the given criteria fills in part of the learners' needs (Paul, 2003).

Limitations of Material Adaptation

Adaptation is a time-consuming process: It calls for in-advance and afterward case studies, action research, surveys, etc. It is not claimed to be a day's task. Such contextual variables as age, social status, gender, ethnicity, race, as well as students' background knowledge, learning needs, learning styles, course objectives, and students' levels are to be put into careful and adequate consideration and study in relation to a specific learning context.

- (a) **Adaptation needs professionalism:** Evaluation in order to adapt the materials to the students' learning context is not an undertaking to be carried out by anyone with any expertise. The people must be skilled in developing materials and have a diagnostic and analytic view of the local learning contexts. Even the teachers must be experienced, knowledgeable and qualified.
- (b) **Adaptation cannot be universally and equally appealing:** Adaptation is a process, which needs to be of local interest. Because of such factors as cultural differences, ethnicity, educational systems, peculiar environments of learning, etc., materials appealing to one learning context may not be similarly attractive to another.
- (c) **Adaptation may be affected by the saturation of flexibility:** Sometimes, the people in charge of adapting materials go to extremes due mostly to lack of enough knowledge of the given materials, unfamiliarity with learning contexts, psychological concerns, fatigue, lack of enough time, personal/political/religious bias, gender favoritism, etc.
- (d) **Adaptation fails to take into account all learners' needs equally:** There is no denying that learners differ in needs. Therefore, these needs must be analyzed in making pedagogical decisions especially materials development. Although needs analysis is an indispensable part of curriculum/materials development, can we adapt the materials by considering all the individual needs of EFL learners in all the learning contexts? Can adaptation take into account all the given learners' psychological, social, affective and learning variables in different learning contexts equally? Of course, not.
- (e) Adaptation cannot establish congruence between learners, teachers, methodologies, administrators, publishers' expectations, as well as those of course

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objectives at the same time. Adaptation seems to have different meanings. For learners, it means facilitation of language learning. For teachers, it is the facilitation of teaching process. Based on the teaching methodologies, it should correspond to pedagogical principles. For administrators, it often means “ease of standardization”. For publishers, it is a matter of making profits. And the course objectives require that adaptation fulfill what has been planned for the given course. Therefore, it seems to be almost impossible to match all these attitudes in order to make an effective process of materials adaptation.

- (f) **Adaptation fails to be carried out on all types of materials:** Only reading texts containing no political, religious, legal and ethical restrictions are apt to be adapted to EFL learners’ context. We cannot modify the listening materials, which carry the native accents and oral discourse. If we make some cuts on such materials, learners may feel gaps easily in the events of the listening tracks or contents. Although there are, in some cases, misunderstandings in such authentic materials, this problem can be solved by skilled teachers through listening comprehension techniques.
- (g) **Adaptation may be impinged on by the materials adaptor’s tastes:** Sometimes people tend to select for adaptation those materials they regard as suitable only because the topics are their favorites, overlooking the role of students’ needs and interests and course objectives. This occurs when learners feel that the materials selected and adapted are of no interest to them. McDonough argues in general that materials are therefore learning resources and embody the course writers’ views on how languages are learnt, what exercise type and tasks work, and what both the learner and teacher should do in the classroom and in their own preparation (Rubdy, 2003).

Conclusion

Textbooks are obviously the life-blood of a lively, interactive and meaningful language classroom along with other available, relevant materials. It is very important that while choosing materials for language class, teachers have to be very careful about the materials, activities and methods, be selective about authentic and genuine materials to facilitate learning the four language skills, ensure that the content or topic convey relevant messages that enrich and widen students’ use of the ‘real world’ language and lastly pay attention to the background, needs and expectations of various target groups. Moreover, in the context of globalized world it is crucial to

provide ideas to the language learners about different nations and cultures to enhance cross cultural understanding. Similarly, teachers have to be mindful about learners' cultural sensitivity. Therefore, in selecting materials it is important to create a good blending of materials collecting from various sources such as: local, target language culture, multicultural and universal contexts which will enhance more meaningful teaching learning culture and also reduce unnecessary cultural hegemony.

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